

Research Article

An examination of the reflections of Faig Sujaddinov's compositional works in Azerbaijani media

Çilenay Huseynova¹

Department of Music History and Theory, Institute of Architecture and Art, Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences, Baku, Azerbaijan

Article Info

Received: 12 October 2025
Accepted: 14 December 2025
Online: 30 December 2025

Keywords

Azerbaijani media
Azerbaijani music culture
Faig Sujaddinov

Abstract

This research examines the reflection of the compositional works of Azerbaijani People's Artist and Order of Merit recipient Faig Sujaddinov in Azerbaijani media. The main aim of the research is to reveal the composer's artistic identity, the thematic and stylistic characteristics of his works, and to evaluate the place of these works in the cultural context. Within the scope of the study, Faig Sujaddinov's productions, especially in the field of song composition, are examined; how his works are represented through media, concerts, albums, and various artistic events is analyzed. It has been determined that F. Sujaddinov's works are shaped primarily around three main axes: melodicism, lyricism, and deep emotional expression. While the theme of love holds an important place in the composer's songs, love of homeland and nation is also prominently featured, especially in his patriotic works. In this respect, Sujaddinov's music exhibits a holistic structure that reflects both individual emotions and social values. The fact that Faig Sujaddinov's works have been performed by different artists in different periods has ensured that his music has been embraced by a wide audience. In addition to his songs, his symphonic and instrumental works have made significant contributions to Azerbaijani musical culture. Media reviews and artist comments demonstrate that the composer's works have strengthened their place in cultural memory. In conclusion, this study reveals the importance of Faig Sujaddinov's compositions within Azerbaijani musical culture and offers a multi-dimensional evaluation of his works through their media coverage.

3108-3749/ © 2025 the Authors.
Published by Genc Bilge (Young Wise)
Pub. Ltd. This is an open access article
under the CC BY license.

To cite this article

Huseynova, Ç. (2025). An examination of the reflections of Faig Sujaddinov's compositional works in Azerbaijani media. *Scientific Studies: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 1(2), 51-56. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21040820>

Introduction

Faig Sujaddinov, a People's Artist of Azerbaijan and recipient of the Order of Glory, holds a unique and distinguished place in the history of Azerbaijani musical culture through his song creativity, characterized by an individual style, profound spirit, and expressive lyrics. The composer's creative output spans a wide spectrum of genres. Among his works, concertos for piano and symphony orchestra, string quartets, concertos for piano and chamber orchestra, a Scherzo for chamber orchestra, the chamber music work "Atatürk" for choir and symphony orchestra, as well as jazz compositions written for various ensembles are particularly noteworthy. At the same time, songs constitute a significant portion of his artistic production, as Sujaddinov began his compositional career with song writing. All of his songs are built upon unique melodies. This distinctive melodicism reflects human emotions and excitement, inner world, love of life, feelings, and vocal expression. Perhaps the reason for the wide popularity of his songs lies in his deep sensitivity and heartfelt devotion as a music lover. One of the defining features that distinguishes the composer from others is precisely the melodic beauty and delicacy inherent in his songs.

¹ Research Assistant, Department of Music History and Theory, Institute of Architecture and Art, Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences, Baku, Azerbaijan.
E-mail: cilenaybedelova@icloud.com ORCID: 0009-0006-1301-4921

Photo 1. Faig Sujaddinov (from the author's personal archive)

When examining Faig Sujaddinov's songs, it can be observed that they are essentially characterized in three main directions: musicality and melodicism, lyricism, and profound emotional depth. It can be confidently stated that the songs and other works of F. Sujaddinov are clearly and distinctly differentiated by their stylistic features. Although the composer has written more than 100 songs, he continues to compose and create in this genre tirelessly. Over time, both in the past and in the present, his songs have been frequently performed and have been met with great enthusiasm and affection by a wide audience. The composer's first song, "Seni Gördüm," was performed by the late singer Gulaga Mammadov (Azerbaijani Love Romances, 2002).

Photo 2. Gulaga Memmedov (Web 1)

One of the most beloved songs of the youth period is the composition "Neylersen Menye." We would like to provide our readers with some additional information about this song. This work by the composer is among the songs that have gained a lasting place in people's hearts. With lyrics written by Nurida Ateş and performed by the late İlhamə Guliyeva, a People's Artist of Azerbaijan, the song continues to be loved today. Having been performed by numerous singers, it has become a favorite among many Turkic communities. Another lyrical song by Faig Sujaddinov is "Kaman Ayrılık," which is also included among İlhamə Guliyeva's favored repertoire.

Photo 3. İlhamə Quliyeva (Web 2)

Photo 4. Baba Veziroğlu (Web 3)

Faig Sujaddinov's songs such as "Vatan Payı Yok," "Seni Özledim," "Seni Gördüm," "Aşk Yaşa Bakmaz," "Siyah Gözler," "Sensiz Ne Yaparım," "Yaşayamam," "Vatan Askeri," "Şarkım," "Mutluluk Şarkısı," "Yalan," "Barış Güvercini," and "Beni Unutursan," among others, are also among the most beloved works of the Azerbaijani people. As can be seen, the theme of love occupies an important place in the composer's works. Alongside this, the theme of homeland also holds a broad and significant position in his compositions. As Faig Sujaddinov is deeply devoted to his homeland and devoted to his nation, the central criterion of his works is patriotism. The composer masterfully reflects love for the homeland in both his instrumental and vocal works, and while listening to his instrumental piano composition "Vatan Balladası," it is impossible not to sense the love, longing, and deep emotional attachment in the composer's heart (Azerbaijani Composers, 2000). The works "Andımız Azərbaycan" and "Bu Dünya Bir Sevdə," with

lyrics by academician Rafael Hüseynov, as well as “Bir Diyar Vuruldu,” with lyrics by folk poet Baba Veziroğlu, are also compositions written in a patriotic spirit. Although the public generally recognizes Faig Sujaddinov as a lyrical composer, his works reflecting heroism and patriotism are not limited to songs alone. Some of his symphonic works have been mentioned above. His Piano and Symphony Orchestra Concerto composed in 1990 and his Piano and Chamber Orchestra Concerto composed in 1992 serve as important sources for new generations of music lovers. In 2004, the piano works “Vatandan Pay Olmaz” and “Vatan Balladası” were published, followed by the release of “Qalbm Bir Denizdir” in 2006, the song collection “Sana Kıbrısım” in 2002, and a more developed version of the “Sana Kıbrısım” project in 2004. During his years in Cyprus, Faig Sujaddinov worked on significant projects, culminating in a major work dedicated to the 35th anniversary of the independence of the Republic of Cyprus. It should be noted that both the sheet music collection titled “Kıbrıs’ım Sana” and the project’s album contain 30 songs (Sujaddinov, F., 2006). The composer created these songs using lyrics by prominent Cypriot poets Ayşen Dağlı, Dr. Arif Ali Albayrak, and Bülent Fevziöğlü. After returning to his homeland, he continued to work on new songs, including “Aşk Şiiri” with lyrics by the renowned Azerbaijani poet Cabir Nevrüz, “Azerbaycan” with lyrics by İsmayıl Dadaşov, “Selam Ver” with lyrics by Rafael Hüseynov, “Şarkılar” with lyrics by Vagif Cebayilzade, and others. While “Aşk Şiiri” reflects love felt for an individual, the song “Azerbaycan” beautifully conveys love for the homeland through the dramatic development of its melody. Today, it can be proudly stated that Faig Sujaddinov’s songs, film music, pop stage works, and operettas are loved, appreciated, and have become legendary among a wide audience (World Composers, 1999). Songs such as “Ömür” and “Gözlerin” performed by People’s Artist Samir Jafarov, “Bahar Çiçeği” performed by People’s Artist Azer Zeynalov, “Vatan Harayı” performed by People’s Artist Mübariz Tağıyev, “İncime” performed by Honored Artist Reşad İlyasov, “Deli Mahabbatım” and “Bu Sevdamız” performed by young artist Zabita Aliyeva, “Kalbm Bir Denizdir” performed by Arzu Aliyeva, as well as “Eşq Mehrabi” and “Duya Podildim” performed by other artists, have been released. During the period of independence, songs such as “Tenha Gül,” “Üzür Məni Zamanələr,” “Tanrı Payı,” “Ürək Qəm Bağlar,” and many others, with lyrics by the well-known playwright, publisher, and poet Ali Valioğlu, were performed by the young composer and performer Çilenay Hüseynova (the author of this study) and many other artists.

Photo 5. “Qalbm Bir Denizdir” (My hearth is sea) Album

While listening to the songs on this album, a sense of peace and tranquility reaches deep into the human heart. In these songs, the composer elevates feelings of love to the highest level and succeeds in touching the hearts of listeners. Through the works of poet, publisher, playwright, and renowned writer Ali Valioğlu, the unity of music and poetry finds new life in the performers’ interpretations. I have collaborated with Faig Sujaddinov on many projects. Performing the songs of such a composer feels natural to me, and as a young performer and composer, this experience is both a source of pride and a responsibility.

Photo 6. Çilenay Husynova and F. Sujaddinov (from the author's personal archive)

Photo 7. Çilenay Husynova and F. Sujaddinov (from the author's personal archive)

The renowned composer Faig Sujaddinov is one of the artists who has left an indelible mark on the history of Azerbaijani musical culture through his distinctive style, spirit, and lyrical breath. We wish the composer good health, continued creative success, and inexhaustible energy. Below, we present the lyrics of the song titled “Gideceğim,” composed by F. Sujaddinov with lyrics written by Zülfügar Şahseven (Web 3).

Azerbaijani

Sən məni nə vaxtsa itirəcəksən,
Ömür vərəqindən silinəcəyəm,
Yox, demərəm, səni unudacağam,
Mən səni sevərək tərək edəcəyəm.

Nəqərat:

Sən mənim həyatda çarəsiz dərdim,
Heç vaxt duymadığım ilk məhəbbətim.
Görünür, xoşbəxtlik deyil qismətim,
Mən səni sevərək tərək edəcəyəm.
Nə qədər gözəl olsa da bu həyat,
Nə qədər şirin olsa da yaşamaq,
Səninlə günü gündən çətin olacaq,
Mən səni sevərək tərək edəcəyəm.

Böyük bir günahdır bu məhəbbətim,
Acı göz yaşlarım, qəmli həsrətim.
Sahili görünməz mavi dənizin,
Mən səni sevərək tərək edəcəyəm.

English

You will one day lose me,
I will be erased from the pages of life.
No, I will not say that I will forget you,
I will leave you loving you.

Chorus:

You are my helpless sorrow in life,
My first love I have never truly known.
It seems that happiness is not my destiny,
I will leave you loving you.
No matter how beautiful this life may be,
No matter how sweet it is to live,
Being with you will grow harder day by day,
I will leave you loving you.

This love of mine is a great sin,
My bitter tears, my sorrowful longing.
Like the shoreless blue sea unseen,
I will leave you loving you.

Photo 8. Our Colleagues and F. Sujaddinov (from the author's personal archive)

Photo 9. After the program recording with F. Sujaddinov (from the author's personal archive)

Conclusion

Azerbaijan is one of the countries that has made significant contributions to world music through its distinguished composers. In addition to the artistic value of a composer's works, examining the visibility of these works and their reflections in the media is of great importance. In this study, from a different perspective shaped by my professional background, the reflections of Faig Sujaddinov's compositional works in Azerbaijani media were examined. Within this framework, the composer's artistic identity and orientations, the codes of his stylistic language, and his role in cultural influence were analyzed. It is evident that Sujaddinov holds a distinguished position in Azerbaijani musical culture, particularly in the field of song composition. This prominence can be attributed to the strong melodic structure of his works, the depth of his lyrical expression, and their emotional intensity, all of which have enabled his music to reach a wide audience and gain visibility in the media.

A clear focus on the themes of love and homeland is observed in Faig Sujaddinov's creative world. While his lyrical songs primarily address individual emotions, longing, and inner experiences, his works centered on the homeland emphasize national identity, love for the country, and social sensitivity. The frequent appearance of Sujaddinov's works in the media, their performance by various artists, and their broad acceptance among the public have increased the

recognition of his compositions within cultural memory. In addition to his songs, his symphonic and instrumental works have also secured their place in Azerbaijani musical culture, serving as valuable resources for younger generations of music enthusiasts. By evaluating the media reflections of the composer's works, this study contributes to a better understanding of one dimension of Faiq Sujaddinov's multidimensional artistic legacy.

Biodata of Author

Çilanay Huseynova was born in Baku. In 1996, she enrolled in the piano department of the Bülbül Secondary Specialized Music School and graduated from this institution in 2007. In the same year, she began her studies at the Baku Music Academy, from which she graduated in 2011. Between 2015 and 2023, Çilanay Hüseyn qızı worked as a lecturer at the Folklore Institute of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences. Accompanied by the "Gorgud Folklore" ensemble, she performed folk songs at state events, television programs, and concerts. In 2018, she released her first album consisting of 12 songs. During the 44-day Patriotic War in 2020, she composed numerous patriotic songs, which led to the release of her second album titled "Karabakh Is Azerbaijan." In 2021, she successfully represented Azerbaijan at an event held in Vienna, Austria, dedicated to the 800th anniversary of Nizami Ganjavi. In 2022, she visited Budapest, Hungary, and successfully represented Azerbaijan at the 7th Turan Congress. Between 2021 and 2022, she obtained a master's degree from the Department of Choral Conducting at the Baku Music Academy. She is actively engaged in compositional activities and is the author of approximately 50 songs. Since February 1, 2023, she has been working as a research assistant at the Institute of Architecture and Art of the Azerbaijan National Music Academy. She is currently conducting research on the scientific study titled "Song Creativity of Azerbaijani Composers in the Period of Independence." She is also the author of four scientific articles focusing on the song creativity of Azerbaijani composers.

References

- Azerbaijani children's songs. (2004). Baku: Nashriyyat Publishing.
 Azerbaijani composers. (2000). Baku: Sharq va Gharb Publishing.
 Azerbaijani love romances. (2002). Baku: Nashriyyat Publishing.
 Azeri, L. (2012, June 22). *A composer whose songs conceal the whisper of the Caspian Sea*. Kültür, 11.
 History of Azerbaijani music. (2020). Baku: Elm ve Tehsil Publishing.
 Sujaddinov, F. (2006). *Azerbaijani composers and musicologists*. Baku.
 World composers. (1999). Baku: Zulfi Brothers Publishing.

Web Sites

- Web 1.** Metbuat.az. (n.d.). *Gulaga Memmedov*. <https://metbuat.az/melumat/taninmis/43/gulaga-memmedov.html>
Web 2. Trend.az. (n.d.). *Azerbaijani culture*. <https://az.trend.az/azerbaijan/culture/2499250.html>
Web 3. Söz Musiqi. (n.d.). *Faiq Sujaddinov – "I Will Leave You Loving You"*. <https://sozmusiqi.wordpress.com/az/composer/faiq-suceddinov/terk-edeceyem/>
Web 4. Kulis.az. (n.d.). *Interview with Baba Veziroğlu*. <https://kulis.az/xeber/media/baba-veziroglu-o-xalq-yazicisi-menim-olum-fermanimi-imzaladi-musahibe-39630>